

Satellite and modelling based snow season time series for Svalbard: Intercomparisons and assessment of accuracy (SATMODSNOW 2)

Hannah Vickers¹, Eirik Malnes¹, Stein Rune Karlsen¹, Tuomo Saloranta², Mari Anne Killie³, Ward van Pelt⁴, Claudia Notarnicola⁵, Laura Stendardi⁵

1 NORCE Norwegian Research Centre AS, Bergen, Norway

2 Norwegian Water and Energy Directorate, Oslo, Norway

3 Norwegian Meteorological Institute, Oslo, Norway

4 University of Uppsala, Uppsala, Sweden

5 Eurac Research, Institute for Earth Observation, Bolzano, Italy

Corresponding author: Hannah Vickers, havi@norceresearch.no

ORCID number: 0000-0002-0765-0490

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1. Introduction

In Svalbard, snow cover characteristics are changing rapidly due to ongoing climate warming and associated trends of increasing temperature and precipitation. These climatic changes have resulted in earlier disappearance of seasonal snow with later onset of snow in autumn, have raised the altitude of the equilibrium line perennial snow (van Pelt et al., 2016), decreased maximum snow depths and increased the frequency of winter rain-on-snow events (Hansen et al., 2011; Peeters et al., 2019; Vickers et al., 2022). During the last few decades, datasets for snow cover and snow water equivalent in Svalbard have been built up through use of both remote sensing methods and snow models. To build a complete, consistent, and accurate picture of snow cover evolution in Svalbard, how it has been changing and is going to change in the future, there is a need to assimilate data from snow models and observations. Remote sensing can provide observations over large spatial areas at higher resolution but lacks temporal consistency due to issues such as cloud cover. While snow models can provide consistent and spatially complete data over large scales, their resolution is often too coarse to accurately represent the true spatial variability in snow cover. Moreover, snow models are often calibrated using remote sensing observations as well as large-scale numerical analysis, while remote sensing observations often rely on models for

validation due to a lack of ground observations over large spatial scales. There is therefore a need to examine the similarities and differences between the different models and sensors, as well as between datasets of different spatial resolution, to determine how they can be used to complement each other and fill in knowledge gaps regarding patterns and changes in snow cover in Svalbard. This work builds on the earlier SESS report chapter SATMODSNOW (Malnes et al., 2021) where snow model products were compared with remote sensing datasets to fulfil two objectives. First, to identify where models and remote sensing datasets differ both temporally and spatially, and second, to cross-compare satellite remote sensing datasets across a range of scales. A long-term goal will be to use high resolution data from newer sensors to downscale and reconstruct long time series of snow cover patterns measured using older, lower resolution sensors. Since the report chapter SATMODSNOW was published, new snow cover datasets have become available, as well as additional years with data building on the existing datasets. In SATMODSNOW2 the earlier analyses are repeated and updated using the additional datasets that are now available. This is done not only to solidify earlier results but also to identify outstanding challenges associated with snow cover mapping and make recommendations for future snow research in Svalbard.

2. The state of snow cover datasets in Svalbard

Several remote sensing and snow model datasets provide coverage over Svalbard, spanning a time frame from 1982 to present day. In the earlier SATMODSNOW report (Malnes et al., 2021) a rigorous description of the available datasets was provided in sections 2.1 and 2.2. In this update we have primarily focused on the datasets that have been updated with additional years of data as well as giving an overview of new datasets that have been analysed since the earlier report. In terms of the two remote sensing datasets, 3 additional years

of MODIS data have been included (2020-2022) while the AVHRR dataset includes 4 additional years of binary snow cover extent (SCE) data, now providing coverage for 2000–2019. The MODIS snow cover fraction dataset with its 500 m spatial resolution, forms the basis for the comparisons with other remote sensing and model datasets in this report. The seNorge snow model (Saloranta, 2016), which earlier covered only full years from 2013–2019, now also includes 3 additional years, while the Energy Balance-Firn Model (EBFM)

provided by Uppsala University (van Pelt et al., 2012; van Pelt et al., 2019) includes 5 more years and covers the same time frame as the MODIS dataset (2000–2022).

In addition, the snow project of the ESA Climate Change Initiative (CCI) programme has resulted in the production of a Daily Snow Cover Fraction on Ground (SCFG) product with worldwide coverage, including Svalbard, at 1 km resolution and is based on MODIS Terra data. A thorough overview of this product as well as the algorithms used to retrieve SCFG are presented by Nagler et al. (2022). While the data source is the same as for the MODIS dataset referred to in this report, the differing retrieval and cloud masking approaches, as well as land and water masks applied to each product, renders a comparison of the two datasets necessary. This study uses version 2.0 of the SCFG product which covers 2000–2020. Since there are no forests in Svalbard, there should be

no difference between the SCFG and MODIS snow cover fraction (SCF) product, which would otherwise observe the top of the canopy. In this study, the CCI SCFG data are remapped to match the 500 m MODIS SCF grid.

To extend the time series of MODIS snow cover fraction, Notarnicola (2022) proposes a hybrid model to merge satellite data and model simulation through a machine learning approach. More specifically, the modelled data are derived from the simulation of the Famine Early Warning Systems Network (FEWS NET) Land Data Assimilation System (FLDAS, <https://ldas.gsfc.nasa.gov/fldas>), which is produced on a monthly basis with global coverage at a spatial resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ ($10 \text{ km} \times 10 \text{ km}$). The model simulations are available from 1982 to present. In the period of overlap with MODIS time series, SCF time series of modelled and MODIS data were compared, and a machine learning approach based on Artificial Neural

Figure 1: Time series of snow-covered fraction (SCF) for all datasets

Figure 2: Scatter plot illustrating the relationship between the MODIS land-averaged SCF and AVHRR land-averaged SCE for the 20 overlapping years of data. Each point represents a daily value.

Networks was used to calibrate the modelled data with MODIS observations to reduce biases and improve the spatial representativeness due to the model coarse resolution. While this dataset is based on the MODIS time series, a major difference in the calculation of the yearly mean SCF is the inclusion of glaciated areas since Notarnicola (2022) focused on snow cover in mountain areas only, while the MODIS dataset of Malnes et al. (2021) considers snow on land areas only.

For all datasets, we have focused on (i) comparisons of the land-averaged snow cover fraction, which is calculated for each day of year and all the years of each dataset and (ii) differences in the number of days with snow cover. The methods used to obtain the land averaged SCF, and duration of snow cover, are already outlined in section 2.3 of the original SESS report chapter (Malnes et al., 2021).

2.1. 2.1 Comparison to other remote sensing datasets

2.1.1. AVHRR (20 years) 2000–2019 (+4 years)

The additional 4 years of binary snow-covered extent (SCE) data did not bring about any new

changes to the earlier derived relationship between MODIS and AVHRR, or the spatial variation in the difference in number of days with snow across the archipelago. We find that the land-averaged SCE in AVHRR is greater than the land-averaged SCF in the MODIS dataset throughout the year, as shown by the time series comparison in Figure 1. This is likely attributable to the large difference in resolution of the two datasets, with the coarse resolution AVHRR sensor not allowing partially covered grid cells to be resolved. The scatter plot in Figure 2 displays the relationship between the MODIS SCF and AVHRR SCE, with a dashed line indicating where values would be equal in both datasets.

2.1.2. CCI SCFG (20 years) 2000–2019

In Figure 3, we illustrate the relationship between the 500 m MODIS SCF product and the ESA CCI SCFG product based on a 1 km grid. The figure also shows the daily cloud cover fractions for the two datasets. The 500 m MODIS SCF is consistently greater than the corresponding 1 km CCI SCFG, with the greatest difference in snow cover at sub-maximum values, typically on the order of around 20% greater than CCI SCFG. The corresponding cloud cover fractions show a significant contrast

Figure 3: Scatter plot illustrating the relationship between the 500 m MODIS SCF, and the ESA CCI 1 km MODIS SCFG dataset (dark blue) and the cloud pixels (grey) detected in each dataset.

in cloud detection in the two datasets, with cloud cover being much greater in the MODIS 500 m product compared to the CCI SCFG product, which generally always detected below 40% cloud cover fraction, while the MODIS 500 m product detected much greater cloud cover of up to 100% on many occasions. However, if snow-covered pixels in the MODIS 500 m product have been incorrectly classified as cloud, giving rise to high cloud detection, one would expect a correction to result in less cloud but greater snow cover, increasing the difference between the two datasets, suggesting that this may not necessarily be the main driver of the observed snow cover fraction differences.

2.1.3. Hybrid model

The “hybrid” dataset which uses machine learning methods to combine MODIS and model measurements provides yearly averages of the land-averaged SCF for mountainous areas of Svalbard, where the SCF is averaged over the hydrological year (1 October – 30 September). Averaged daily land SCF using the MODIS 500

m data was averaged across the hydrological year to compare with this dataset. Figure 4 illustrates the time series for the period 2000–2019. Yearly variations in mean SCF for the two datasets are correlated with each other; however, the hybrid MODIS-model SCF product is typically 5-10% greater than the 500 m MODIS product. Note that the main differences between the datasets are that the hybrid model (i) does not include any cloud gap filling procedure and (ii) includes glaciers in the yearly average, whereas the MODIS 500 m product is based on non-glacial land areas.

2.2. Comparison with snow model datasets

2.2.1. seNorge (10 years) 2013–2022 (+3 years)

For seNorge, the additional 3 years of data increases the number of data points for comparison by nearly 50% with respect to the 7 years of data that were used in the earlier SESS report. However, the relationship between the land-averaged snow-

Figure 4: Time series of the hybrid MODIS-model SCF and the 500 m MODIS product.

covered area obtained from the seNorge dataset, and the land-averaged snow cover fraction from the MODIS dataset remains largely unchanged compared with the earlier result, as illustrated by Figure 8a of Malnes et al. (2021). For snow cover fractions at the minimum end of the scale, MODIS was typically greater than the seNorge dataset, while the opposite is true at the time of year when snow cover fraction was typically at maximum. Time series of the land-averaged snow cover fraction (Figure 1) reveal that some years exhibited a mismatch in timing of snowmelt onset and onset of snow in autumn between the two datasets, such that snowmelt occurred earlier in MODIS while snow covered area was still at a maximum in seNorge, giving rise to higher snow cover area in seNorge compared to MODIS, but the onset of snow in autumn was also later in seNorge, meaning that MODIS snow-covered fraction was increasing while seNorge snow-covered area was still at a minimum. However, the time series of land-averaged snow cover fraction masks information on the spatial variation in differences in timing of snowmelt/snow-on; Figure 5 displays the difference in number of days with snow cover (SCA or SCF > 50%) between the seNorge dataset

and MODIS dataset. Here it can be seen that across Edgeøya, the seNorge dataset typically has a greater number of days with snow cover compared to MODIS, whereas across low elevation areas in Nordenskiöld Land, seNorge exhibits fewer days with snow compared to MODIS, with differences typically in the range of ± 20 –40 days.

2.2.2. EBFM (23 years) 2000–2022 (+5 years)

Similar to the results of the comparisons between the MODIS SCF and the AVHRR and seNorge datasets, we found that the additional 5 years of snow water equivalent (SWE) data did not change the statistical relationship between the MODIS SCF and SCF derived from the EBFM SWE data; for low SCF days in the EBFM dataset, corresponding MODIS values were typically higher, while for high SCF days in the EBFM dataset, the MODIS values were lower than EBFM. This is likely due to the same reasons as for the seNorge dataset, where the model snow cover can be seen to start snowmelt slightly later than MODIS in several years (2004–2007, 2020–2021), and onset of snow cover lags MODIS in the autumn most years of the overlapping dataset. The result of this time lag in snowmelt and snow onset between the two datasets is a difference in number of days with snow cover that varies spatially across the archipelago as illustrated in Figure 5 (right panel). The EBFM dataset exhibits fewer days with snow compared to MODIS across large parts of Nordenskiöld Land, Nordaustlandet and Edgeøya; however, there are parts of northern Spitsbergen, eastern coastal areas of Nordenskiöld Land and western coastal areas of Edgeøya where there are a greater number of days with snow cover derived from EBFM SWE data compared to the MODIS dataset.

Figure 5: The difference in number of days with snow cover, comparing (a) the seNorge dataset to MODIS and (b) the EBFM model to MODIS. For both models, positive values (blue hues) indicate a greater number of days with snow while negative values (orange-red hues) indicate a greater number of days with snow cover in MODIS.

3. Contributions to interdisciplinarity

Snowmelt patterns – both temporal and spatial – are important for the transport of nutrients into rivers and fjords through surface runoff, as well as determining the timing of onset of vegetation growth in the spring. Seasonal snow cover acts as an important insulator for permafrost; wintertime snowmelt resulting from rain-on-snow events can contribute to degradation of permafrost as well as result in ice crusts that can present a physical barrier to forage for reindeer. Thus, datasets that allow monitoring of snowmelt in both space and time will be of value to research into terrestrial and marine ecological systems in Svalbard.

The long time series of snow models and observations are of importance to climate studies where spatial variations in trends in timing of snow disappearance and onset reflect spatial variations in changes in the large-scale drivers of snowmelt, including those of atmospheric and oceanic origin.

Advancements made since Malnes et al. (2021) primarily comprise the additional years of data made available to the SIOS database, as well as the inclusion of the ESA CCI SCFG dataset.

4. Unanswered questions

On a long-term perspective, the goal is to integrate both model and observations to produce an accurate representation of snow cover dynamics in Svalbard. Differences between different snow models, and between snow models and observations, do not uncover which dataset is more accurate than another; this requires a more thorough validation of each model and remote

sensing method using ground observations. This should enable the development of an optimal method for assimilating observations into models or vice versa. However, since the current availability of consistent time series of ground observations of snow parameters across Svalbard is poor in terms of spatial coverage, development of the ground based observational network is greatly needed.

The findings of this study reveal that the differences in snow cover between models and remote sensing datasets vary spatially across the archipelago, and that models are systematically late with respect to timing of snowmelt and snow onset. However,

without substantial improvement in availability of ground truth measurements, an improvement in both model and remote sensing products is not very probable at present.

5. Recommendations for the future

- Integrate high-resolution datasets e.g. Sentinel 2 with artificial intelligence (AI) methods to downscale coarse resolution data and thus provide more detailed information on snow cover dynamics.
- Increase the availability and diversity of ground truthing datasets. These could include more unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) borne surveys providing high resolution snow observations as well as measurements of snow temperature and liquid water content.
- Integrate Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) wet snow datasets with snow cover from optical sensors (Vickers et al., 2022) to improve snow cover detection during the melting period on overcast days. SAR can also provide information on melting phases (Marin et al., 2020) which is important in the context of water resource management.

6. Data availability

Dataset	Parameter	Period	Location	Metadata access (URL)	Dataset provider
MODIS	Snow cover fraction	2000-2022	Svalbard	https://thredds.met.no/thredds/arcticdata/infraNOR.html?dataset=norcesnowcover-agg	NORCE
AVHRR	Snow cover extent	1982-2019	Svalbard	https://thredds.met.no/thredds/catalog/metusers/mariak/sios_SvalSCE_dataset/catalog.html	METNO
EBFM	Snow water equivalent	1957-2022	Svalbard	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.13142840.v2	Uppsala University
seNorge	Snow covered area	2012-2022	Svalbard	www.senorge.no	NVE Jess Joar Andersen (jea@nve.no)
CCI	Snow cover fraction on ground	2000-2019	Worldwide	https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/8847a05eeda646a29da58b42bdf2a87c	ESA CCI
Hybrid MODIS/model	Snow cover fraction	1982-2022	Worldwide	Available on request	EURAC claudia. notarnicola@eurac.edu

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